

Total Lipase Assay Kit Instruction

1. Reagent Compositions and Preparation

	Compositions	100T/48 Samples	50T/24 Samples	Preservation Period
Reagent I	Powder	4 Bottles	2 Bottles	4°C for 3 months
	Solvent	1 Bottle×10ml	1 Bottle×5ml	
Preparation of Reagent I Solution: Dissolve each bottle of powder with 1.5ml solvent and mix thoroughly. The solution can be preserved at 4°C.				
Reagent II	Solution	2 Bottles×6ml	1 Bottle×6ml	4°C for 3 months
Reagent III	Solution	2 Bottles×6ml	1 Bottle×6ml	
Reagent IV	Solute A	1 Bottle×0.5ml	1 Bottle×0.5ml	
	Solvent B	1 Bottle×60ml	1 Bottle×30ml	
Preparation of Reagent IV Solution: Dissolve desirable amount of solute A with solvent B at the ratio of 1:200 (v/v) prior to use. Warm at 37°C for 10 min after preparation.				
Reagent V	Solution A	2 Bottles×4ml	1 Bottle×4ml	4°C for 3 months
	Solution B	1 Bottle×4ml	1 Bottle×4ml	
	Solution C	2 Bottles×30ml	1 Bottle×30ml	
Preparation of Reagent V Solution: Blend solution A, B and C with the ratio 2:1:17 (volume) and the mixture appears to be transparent. Prepare the exact amount desired and the excess amount cannot be mixed with the freshly prepared solution. Warm the solution at 37°C for 10 min before use. Also, please strictly follow the sequence of addition as A, B and C and mix after each addition.				
Reagent VI	Extract	4 Bottles×100ml	3 Bottles×100ml	4°C for 3 months
Reagent VII	Powder A	3 Bottles	2 Bottles	
	Solvent B	3 Bottles×10ml	2 Bottles×10ml	
	Solution C	1 Bottle×0.5ml	1 Bottle×0.5ml	
Preparation of Reagent VII Solution (Chromogenic Agent): Dissolve each bottle of powder with 10ml solvent B and the add solution C to the mixture with the ratio 1(C):100 (v/v) right before use. Prepare exact amount needed as the chromogenic agent is unstable and thus the excess amount cannot be preserved for further use. The mixture of A and B, however, can be preserved at -20°C.				
Palmitic Acid	Solute	3 Bottles of Powder	3 Bottles of Powder	4°C for 3 months
	Solvent	1 Bottle×60ml	1 Bottle×60ml	
Preparation of 2mM palmitic acid stock solution: Dissolve one bottle of powder with solvent to the final volume of 10ml and mix the solution thoroughly.				
Preparation of 0.5mM palmitic standard solution: Dilute the stock solution with solvent to 4 times the initial stock solution volume and the final concentration is 0.5mM.				

2. Procedures of Measurement

I. Pre-treatment

- Weigh the tissues precisely and add physiological saline with the ratio of 1:9 (w/v) and homogenize the mixture in an ice water bath. Centrifuge at 2,500 rpm for 10 min and extract the supernatant for measurement.
- Serum samples can be measured directly.

II. Procedures

Note: The reagent VI should be transferred via glass pipette. Disposable tips are disfavored.

Note: Liquid from lower layer after centrifugation should be sucked with glass pipette or injector. Use of air displacement pipettes with disposable tips is unacceptable.

Compositions (ml)	Blank	Standard	Lipoprotein Lipase (LPL)	Hepatic Lipase (HL)
DDW	0.2	0.15		
0.5mM Standard		0.05		
Sample			0.05	0.05
Reagent I			0.5	0.5
Shake to mix the solution				
Reagent II			0.1	
Reagent III				0.1
Shake to mix the solution				
Reagent IV	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5
Vortex and warm in a water bath at 37°C for 20 min				
Reagent V	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5
Vortex for 10 s and warm in a water bath at 37°C for 10 min				
Reagent VI	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.0
See the procedures listed below				
Extract from Lower layer	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
Reagent VII	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2

Mix and set aside the mixture for 5 min. Regulate the spectrophotometer with reagent VI and record the absorbed optical density (OD) at 550 nm with 0.5 cm path length. Measure OD values for Lipoprotein Lipase and Hepatic Lipase simultaneously.

Detailed Procedures after Reagent VI Addition

- Blend the mixture thoroughly for 2-5 min. The blending is not completed until the bottom of the tube appears to be cream color and the mixture will not separate immediately after stopping the blending.
- Addition of reagent VI should be completed with glass pipette. Plastic containers are unacceptable.
- Centrifuge at 3,500 rpm for 10 min after the completion of blending. The result mixture should be layered clearly. Otherwise, the mixture should be re-blended and

centrifuged again.

4. Remove the supernatant and the solidified layer in middle with glass pipette.
5. Transfer the solution at bottom layer with glass pipette. The glass pipette should be washed 2-3 times with absolute ethanol followed by 2-3 times cleanings by reagent VI. Warm at 37°C for 1-2 min if turbidity is observed.
6. Extract 1 ml solution obtained from step 5 and add chromogenic agent.
7. The cuvettes should be washed by absolute ethanol followed by reagent VI.
8. All methods are carried out with glass equipment. No plastic equipment is allowed.

3. Calculation Formula and Example

I. Serum Samples

a. Definition

One enzyme activity unit is defined as 1μmol fatty acid generated with 1ml reaction volume within an hour.

b. Formula

$$LPL \text{ Activity } \frac{U/ml}{U/ml} = \frac{OD_{LPL} - OD_{Blank}}{OD_{Standard} - OD_{Blank}} \times \frac{C_{Standard}}{(500\mu M)} \times CoD \div \frac{Time}{1/3h} \div 1000$$

$$HL \text{ Activity } \frac{U/ml}{U/ml} = \frac{OD_{HL} - OD_{Blank}}{OD_{Standard} - OD_{Blank}} \times \frac{C_{Standard}}{(500\mu M)} \times CoD \div \frac{Time}{1/3h} \div 1000$$

$$Total - Lipase \text{ Activity } \frac{U/ml}{U/ml} = \frac{LPL \text{ Activity } U/ml}{U/ml} + \frac{HL \text{ Activity } U/ml}{U/ml}$$

Note: CoD represents the coefficient of dilution.

c. Example

0.05 ml mouse serum adding Heparin for anticoagulation purpose was measured and the OD values are 0.028, 0.065, 0.062 and 0.058 respectively.

$$LPL \text{ Activity } \frac{U/ml}{U/ml} = \frac{0.062 - 0.028}{0.065 - 0.028} \times 500\mu M \times 1 \div 1/3h \div 1000 = 1.378 U/ml$$

$$HL \text{ Activity } \frac{U/ml}{U/ml} = \frac{0.058 - 0.028}{0.065 - 0.028} \times 500\mu M \times 1 \div 1/3h \div 1000 = 1.216 U/ml$$

$$Total - Lipase \text{ Activity } \frac{U/ml}{U/ml} = 1.378U/ml + 1.216U/ml = 2.594U/ml$$

II. Tissue Samples

a. Definition

One enzyme activity unit is defined as 1μmol fatty acid generated with 1mg proteins in tissues within an hour.

b. Formula

$$\text{LPL Activity} = \frac{OD_{LPL} - OD_{Blank}}{OD_{Standard} - OD_{Blank}} \times \frac{C_{Standard}}{(500\mu\text{M})} \times CoD \div \frac{Time}{1/3h} \div \frac{Protein\ Con}{mg/L}$$

$$\text{HL Activity} = \frac{OD_{HL} - OD_{Blank}}{OD_{Standard} - OD_{Blank}} \times \frac{C_{Standard}}{(500\mu\text{M})} \times CoD \div \frac{Time}{1/3h} \div \frac{Protein\ Con}{mg/L}$$

$$\text{Total - Lipase Activity} = \frac{\text{LPL Activity}}{U/mg} + \frac{\text{HL Activity}}{U/mg}$$

c. Example

Mouse hepatic tissues was treated and 10% tissue homogenate was centrifuged. 0.05 ml supernatant was measured and the OD values are 0.028, 0.065, 0.223 and 0.218 respectively. The protein concentration of 10% hepatic tissue homogenate is 9.1mg/ml.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{LPL Activity} &= \frac{0.223 - 0.028}{0.065 - 0.028} \times 0.5\mu\text{mol/ml} \times 1 \div 1/3h \div 9.1\text{mg/ml} \\ &= 0.869 U/mg \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{HL Activity} &= \frac{0.218 - 0.028}{0.065 - 0.028} \times 0.5\mu\text{mol/ml} \times 1 \div 1/3h \div 9.1\text{mg/ml} \\ &= 0.846 U/mg \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Total - Lipase Activity} = 0.869U/mg + 0.846U/mg = 1.715U/mg$$

4. Principle of Measurement

Lipoprotein lipase (LPL) and hepatic lipase (HL) can catalyze the hydrolysis of triglyceride and the product of the reaction is glycerol and free fatty acid (FFA). The amount of free fatty acid can be determined in the presence of reagent V and thus the activity of LPL and HL can be calculated.

As a kind of glycoprotein, the activity of hepatic lipase need not to be activated by apolipoprotein C-II or other ions and the activity will not be inhibited by protamine or high concentration of salt. According to this, the LPL activity and HL activity can be measured separately.

5. Significance of Measurement

LPL is attached to the luminal surface of endothelial cells in capillaries by heparan sulfated proteoglycans and its main function is to catalyze the hydrolysis of triglyceride, such as those found

in chylomicrons (CM) and very low-density lipoproteins (VLDL). And thus plays an important role in degradation of these lipoproteins.

HL is expressed on the surface of endothelial cells in liver. It plays an important role in degradation of degradation of intermediate-density lipoproteins (IDL) and high-density lipoproteins (HDL)